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Abbreviations list

AAI	Authentication and authorization infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
ARK	Archival Resource Key
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
CMDI	Component Metadata Infrastructure
CRIS	Current Research information System
CSMD	Core Scientific Metadata Model
CSV	Comma-separated values
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DRIS	Directory of Research Information Systems,
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HiPS	Hierarchical Progressive Survey (IVOA)
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ICT	Information and communications technology
IF	Interoperability Framework
IVOA	International Virtual Observatory Alliance
JATS	Journal Article Tagging Suite (NISO standard)
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LOM	Learning Object Metadata
maDMP	Machine-Actionable Data Management Plan
MFA	Multi-factor authentication
MSCR	Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PDF	Portable Document Format
PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Profile Interface
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SKG	Science Knowledge Graphs
SSO	Single Sign On
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings
TAP	Table Access Protocol
URI	Universal Resource Identifier
URN	Universal Resource Name
UWS	Universal Worker System
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XSD	XML Schema Definition

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

As the landscape of research data management evolves, ensuring interoperability among tools is critical for effective data sharing and utilisation across diverse platforms. This deliverable focuses on the compliance of tools engaged in the OSTrails project with the OSTrails Pathways and Interoperability Framework. It evaluates the compliance of **Data Management Planning (DMP) platforms, Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), FAIR assessment tools, and other supporting tools** (such as CRIS or repositories) with the OSTrails Interoperability Framework. The aim is to understand current technological alignments, identify gaps, and provide a foundation for future development.

Key results presented in this report are based on the detailed **analysis of 38 tools**, which include DMP platforms, SKGs, FAIR assessment tools, and other supporting tools. The other tools contain two further important subgroups: Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) and Repositories. We **identified core technologies and standards** that most of the tools already use. Furthermore, we identified gaps: comprehensive notification systems, variability in provenance documentation, and the need for ongoing alignment with emerging standards were identified, indicating a need for further elaboration to fulfil the OSTrails Pathways (Reichmann et al., 2024) and OSTrails IF requirements.

The methodology involved a **systematic evaluation of each tool's compliance towards IF and interoperability means**. This process began with the compilation of a Master Table, clearly capturing all tools within the project and their relation to WP2 or WP4 (pilots). Subsequently, we created a flashcard presentation of each tool, serving as a central point containing essential information about the tool. A per-tool analysis was then conducted to systematically assess each tool's compliance with the interoperability framework. This analysis aggregated information from the individual per-tool analysis documents. By examining the existing alignment between the tools and their **relation to the current OSTrails Interoperability Framework (IF)**, as described in the Milestone M4 report¹, we were able to consolidate and summarise our findings.

This document begins with a detailed description of the methodology, including task timelines and examples of each step in the approach. It then focuses on each type of tool (DMP, SKG, FAIR, other), listing the tools analysed, summarising their analysis in terms of technologies employed, data models and formats, integration capabilities, and expectations from Commons and Plans. Interoperability is then analysed also with respect to the OSTrails IF. The document concludes with the results, describing the core technologies identified across all the participating tools, the gaps identified in relation to OSTrails Pathways and the Interoperability Framework, and the next steps based on the solid foundation established by this analysis.

¹ [OSTrails_M4_Interim Products Establishment for Cross-Task](#)

1. Methodology

In our methodology, we included a total of 82 tools for WP2 activities. By “tools” in this document we understand software solutions such as applications, libraries, frameworks, services, and related resources. This number includes core tools mentioned in the project proposal as well as those from national and thematic pilots. The breakdown of these tools is as follows: 5 DMP platforms, 10 Science Knowledge Graphs, 11 FAIR assessment tools, 8 CRIS, 18 data repositories, and 30 other tools.

During our analysis:

- 54 tools completed the Flashcard presentation.
- 38 tools underwent a detailed per-tool analysis, which was optional for pilot tools

The per-tool analysis was optional for pilot tools but mandatory for inclusion in this assessment. As a result, not all 82 tools were included, as some lacked crucial details. Only those tools that underwent the detailed per-tool analysis were included in this analysis.

Conducting an analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework Tools Compliance is crucial for several reasons, all pivotal to the project's continued success, development, and output quality. The interoperability framework and pathways are the backbone of the OSTrails project, delineating the essential connections and the quality attributes these connections must exhibit. The Plan-Track-Assess Framework² refers to a high-level, tool-independent structure designed to support the management of Digital Objects (DOs) in alignment with FAIR principles. The Plan-Track-Assess Pathways (Reichmann et al., 2024) refer to the abstracted representations of how users interact with the components of the PTA Framework (DMPs, SKGs, and FAIR assessment tools) to manage Digital Objects. These pathways outline the specific workflows or actions that users can perform, showing the interplay between different tools as they are employed by different user groups in the research lifecycle. They provide recommendations for standards, formats, and protocols, which are critical for ensuring seamless communication and data exchange across diverse systems and platforms.

However, while the Interoperability Framework offers a theoretical foundation and design principles, the practical implementation and specific design of these connections are the subsequent steps we must undertake. This is where our analysis comes into play. By examining the existing tools within the OSTrails project, as well as those outside it, we can gain a comprehensive understanding of the current technological landscape. Furthermore, this analysis helps in identifying gaps and areas for improvement. By understanding what is currently available and how well these tools align with our interoperability framework, we can pinpoint where additional development or integration work is needed. This proactive approach not only enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of our project but also helps in mitigating potential issues that could arise from incompatibility or non-compliance with the interoperability standards.

² [OSTrails_M4_Interim Products Establishment for Cross-Task Collaboration_v1.0](#)

Figure 1. Diagram of Inputs for the Analysis.

As shown in **Figure 1**, we have taken a several steps towards this analysis to systematically identify, cluster, and analyse the tools:

1. **Master Table Compilation:** We started by creating a master table that captured information about different organisations and their respective tools. This table included tools from the national and thematic pilots involved in the project. The master table served as a centralized repository of all the tools, facilitating easier reference and analysis. We also needed to distinguish expectations for a specific tool based on participation in the project (mainly “core” tools represented directly in WP2 and additional tools coming from pilots). Finally, as tools evolve over time also outside of this project, we expect renaming, additions, and deletions in the master table (and also the project itself).
2. **Flashcard Presentations:** We then requested representatives of each tool to prepare a flashcard presentation. This mandatory one-slide presentation provided very basic information about the tool, including key functionalities, primary use cases, and relevant links. These flashcards were instrumental in quickly grasping the essence of each tool without delving into overly detailed documentation. If anyone wants to discover what a tool does, the flashcard is the first point to reach.

3. **Per-Tool Analysis:** The final preparatory step involved developing an outline for a detailed per-tool interoperability analysis. This outline was designed to address the primary interoperability questions, ensuring that we collected comprehensive knowledge about each tool. Key areas of focus included compatibility with existing standards, supported data formats, integration capabilities, and any known interoperability issues. This structured approach allowed us to systematically assess each tool's compliance with the interoperability framework.
4. **Analysis of the OSTrails IF Compliance:** This document is the culmination of our efforts, aggregating information from the individual per-tool analysis documents. By examining the existing alignment between the tools and their relation to the current OSTrails Interoperability Framework as described in Milestone M4, we were able to consolidate and summarize our findings. In subsequent iterations, feedback was solicited from tool representatives and other colleagues involved in the OSTrails IF. This collaborative effort ensured that the analysis was refined and shaped into its final form, incorporating suggestions for improvements and addressing any identified gaps.

The information gathered through these steps was meticulously reviewed and synthesized into the current document. The analysis presented herein provides a detailed overview of the interoperability compliance of the tools, while the annex includes the partial per-tool analyses. This structured approach ensures that our findings are comprehensive and actionable, providing a solid foundation for the next phase of the OSTrails project.

1.1. Onboarding of Tools

During the initial stages of the project, we quickly realized that there were significant differences between the tools outlined in the proposal and the many additional tools contributed by various pilots. This was an anticipated outcome, given the dynamic nature of the project and the ongoing contributions from national and thematic pilots. To manage this influx of tools and ensure a consistent approach to their integration, we developed a comprehensive Tools Onboarding document (Annex A). This document provides detailed instructions on the steps that new tools should take to align with the OSTrails interoperability framework, including necessary compliance checks, integration protocols, and documentation requirements. The onboarding process ensures that every tool, regardless of its origin, meets the project's standards and can seamlessly interact with other tools within the OSTrails ecosystem.

Moreover, the Tools Onboarding document includes guidelines for modifying or decommissioning tool metadata, acknowledging that the tools' landscape will continue to evolve throughout the project. These instructions ensure that any changes are systematically managed, minimizing disruption and maintaining the integrity of the overall framework. Recognizing the project's iterative nature, we also committed to continually developing and updating this document as more tools are introduced and additional outputs are generated. This proactive approach allows us to adapt to new

developments and maintain a robust and flexible interoperability framework that supports the project's long-term goals.

1.2. The Master Table

As part of our methodology, we created a master table to systematically capture and organise information about the various tools and their respective organisations involved in the project. Early in our efforts, it became clear that the scope and variety of tools extended beyond those initially outlined in the proposal, especially with numerous contributions from national and thematic pilots. Anticipating this diversity, we designed the master table to serve as a centralized repository, facilitating easier reference and analysis of the tools. The table includes critical attributes such as tool name, organisation, core functionality, pilot origin, compliance status, and links to additional documentation.

The master table also distinguishes between "core" tools explicitly mentioned in the Work Package 2 proposal and those added later from pilot projects. This differentiation helps set appropriate expectations and prioritizes our analysis efforts. Given the dynamic nature of the project, we also included provisions for updating the master table to reflect changes such as renaming, additions, and deletions of entries in the spreadsheet. This ensures that our records remain accurate and up-to-date throughout the project lifecycle.

Figure 2. Diagram of entities and its attributes captured in the master table.

Figure 2 illustrates the entities, attributes, and relationships captured in the master table. Notice, that we assigned a numerical ID to every tool as we foresee changes in naming during this project. These IDs can be used to refer to a specific tool unambiguously within this document. This visualization aids in understanding the structure and connections of the tools, supporting informed decision-making as we move forward with the project. The

current version of the master table is included in Annex B. We included two significant subclasses of Other tools (CRIS and Repository) which are non-disjoint but also not-complete; therefore, it is possible to have a tool that is just Other (not CRIS nor Repository) but on the other hand, it is possible that there is a tool which is Other and also acting as both CRIS and Repository. Same applies that a tool can be acting as DMP Platform, SKG, and Other which is theoretically possible and may happen in the future; however, there is no such tool at this point included.

1.3. Tools Flashcards

To streamline the initial assessment of each tool, i.e., landscaping of the tools within our project, we requested representatives from each organisation to prepare a flashcard presentation. This mandatory one-slide presentation captured essential information about the tool, including primary functionalities, use cases, compliance with interoperability standards, and links to further resources. This concise format allowed us to quickly understand the core aspects of each tool without delving into extensive documentation, making the initial review process more efficient.

CESSDA ELST: Basic info **cessda**
ELST Thesaurus

- CESSDA European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELST), <https://thesauri.cessda.eu/elsst-4/en/>
- ELST is a broad-based, multilingual thesaurus for the social sciences
- Web application with frontend, backend (REST API)
- Who develops it (in OSTrails)
 - CESSDA (contact person: Alen Vodopijavec)
- https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/services/eosc.cessda-eric.elsst_european_language_social_sciences_thesaurus
- Other essential resources:
 - User guide: <https://elsst.cessda.eu/>
 - REST-API: <https://thesauri.cessda.eu/rest/v1/swagger.json>

Figure 3. Flashcard presentation of CESSDA ELST tool.

The flashcard presentations ensured we gathered consistent and comparable information across all tools, aiding in their clustering and analysis. Standardizing the format helped us identify commonalities and differences, facilitating a more organized evaluation. **Figure 3** presents an example of a flashcard, showcasing the typical structure and key information included, such as the tool's name, involved stakeholders, core functions, and relevant links. Additionally, more slides with relevant information could be voluntarily added. The visual representation demonstrates the effectiveness of the flashcard approach in providing a clear and accessible overview of each tool. We include merged slide deck of all provided tool flashcard in Annex C.

1.4. Analysis Iterations

The analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework (IF) Compliance represents the culmination of our efforts to systematically evaluate each tool's alignment with the project's interoperability standards. This document aggregates the detailed findings from the per-tool analysis documents (Annex D), examining how each tool aligns with the OSTrails IF as described in Milestone M4. Basically, the per-tool analyses act as tool interviewing to gather specific information about technological choices, interoperability means, and also plans and expectations; therefore, it is another landscaping step, such as the flashcard presentations of the tools, for uncovering state of the art for requirements specifications (we also use the MoSCoW prioritisation³). By consolidating this information, we are able to summarize the current state of interoperability across the project, identifying both strengths and areas for improvement.

Figure 4. Timeline of the Analysis Activities in OSTrails WP2.

As shown in **Figure 4** the analysis process was iterative, involving multiple rounds of feedback and refinement. Initially, tool representatives and other stakeholders provided input based on the preliminary findings. Authors of the per-tool analyses are included as contributors of this document. Their inputs and feedback were crucial to identify gaps, correct inaccuracies, and enhance the overall robustness of the analysis. Subsequent iterations incorporate these insights, allowing us to shape the document into its final form.

Additionally, we provide common insights and clustered the tools by type, according to the project proposal and structure of WP2, to offer a more structured overview. The clusters include Data Management Plan (DMP) platforms, Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), FAIR assessment tools, and other supporting tools. This categorization helps in understanding the specific interoperability challenges and requirements for each type of tool, supporting informed decision-making and continuous improvement within the OSTrails project.

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MoSCoW_method

2. DMP Platforms

Data Management Plan (DMP) platforms are integral to the OSTrails plan-track-assess framework⁴ by ensuring effective research data management that incorporates FAIR principles throughout the project lifecycle. Specifically, they play a crucial role in the **plan** phase, where they facilitate the planning and documentation of data management practices.

2.1. DMP Platforms Included

The analysis included three DMP platforms. These platforms were:

- **Argos/OpenDMP** (ID001, <https://argos.openaire.eu>), based on OpenDMP open-source software, simplifies the management of DMPs and allows the creation of actionable DMPs that can be freely exchanged among infrastructures. Integrated within the OpenAIRE platform and available through the OpenAIRE Service and EOSC catalogues, ARGOS enhances the OpenAIRE Research Graph and utilizes external services, sources, and semantics. DMPs can be assigned DOIs, licenses, and be redistributed in a FAIR manner.
- **DAMAP** (ID009, <https://damap.org>) assists researchers in creating machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) by guiding them through Science Europe's Core Requirements with prompts, text suggestions, and pre-filled content. DAMAP aims to be integrated with institutional environments helping pre-filled content and providing suggestions obtained from CRIS applications and other systems. DAMAP delivers the DMP in both Word and JSON formats compliant with RDA recommendations.
- **Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW)** (ID011, <https://ds-wizard.org>) is a platform for collaborative DMPs, comprising knowledge models, document templates, questionnaires, and documents. Knowledge models define the questionnaire structure, guidance, and integration configuration, and can be edited and maintained directly on the platform by data stewards. Document templates, which use the Jinja2 templating language, transform questionnaires into both human-readable and machine-actionable documents, and are typically maintained by researchers. DSW offers broadly accepted DMP templates, like Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe.

In the analysis, we also included contributions from other national and thematic pilots, such as DMPTuuli (ID010) and Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO, ID034). Furthermore, we investigated DMPRoadmap documentation⁵ as that is related to DMPTuuli; however, DMPRoadmap documentation is relevant to other tools forked from the same codebase (e.g. DMPonline, DMPOPIDoR, etc.). While their functionality can

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13145787>

⁵ <https://github.com/DMPRoadmap/roadmap-docs>

differ, if they are able to keep up-to-date with the original codebase, the key points we use here should be valid for those tools as well.

2.2. Summary of Tools Analysis

In this section, we summarise the per-tool analyses of the DMP platforms and confront the main findings with publicly accessible information about other tools (from OSTrails pilots or widely used within the European research environment).

2.2.1. Technologies and Standards

DMP tools use (as expected) different programming languages and frameworks in their code bases:

- Argos: Java (Spring Boot) and TypeScript (Angular);
- DSW: Haskell, Elm, and Python.
- DAMAP: Java (Quarkus) and TypeScript (Angular).
- DMPTuuli (as well as other DMPRoadmap-based solutions): Ruby (Ruby on Rails) and JavaScript (jQuery).
- RDMO: Python (Django) and JavaScript (React).

However, the use of data exchange formats and integration capabilities have significant overlaps:

- **JSON format** for communication and representation of data structures via API,
- XML/YAML/ZIP for internal configurations, packages, and communication with services that require XML format,
- DOCX (OpenXML), PDF and other for exporting DMPs to files (typically human-readable and based on funder templates).

Argos/OpenDMP, DSW, and DAMAP stated that they have **REST APIs** and also use **OpenAPI specification** with **SwaggerUI** to browse the specification. As explained, JSON is mainly used to represent the input/output data structures when working with these APIs. RDMO also has API using Django REST that includes Swagger. DMPRoadmap has as well REST API using JSON format called APIv1 but specified/document in a human-readable way in GitHub wiki.

In terms authentication and authorization, **OpenID Connect** is widely adopted (including RDMO, while DMPTuuli/DMPRoadmap supports OAuth). Argos/OpenDMP, DSW, and RDMO support issuing API keys or tokens for non-human agents (scripts, services, or other tools). Typically, there are system-wide, tenant-specific, or artefact-specific permissions which can be also grouped into (pre-defined) roles. However, permission models differ significantly based on each platform's internal structure.

2.2.2. Data Models and Operations

The internal data model of a tool is the essential characteristic that distinguishes one tool from another one. Some tools focus on data structures closer to DMP Templates of

fundings, which are then hard coded directly in the code base (DMPRoadmap/RDMO). Some strive for flexibility by having structures like templates, blueprints, knowledge models, or document template (Argos/OpenDMP, DSW). Finally, DAMAP has data model directly based on the RDA DMP Common Standard.

That said, the three platforms that performed the per-tool analysis are committed to **RDA DMP Common Standard for maDMPs**⁶. Tools support import and export of the JSON representation at least partly or with respect to the internal representation of a DMP (i.e. what the users can provide in the specific platform). DSW supports also an RDF representation (together with JSON as standalone document template). RDMO has an additional plugin for maDMP export. DMPTuuli has the same maDMP-capabilities as DMPRoadmap.

Although DMP-related information is captured and stored differently within each platform, it can be presented using a similar or even the same format and structure. This is valid not only for presenting (i.e. exporting), but also for getting the DMP-related information into the platforms (i.e. importing). In their real usage, DMPs are employed for more actions, including partial import, change of settings and sharing, versioning, etc. These other tasks are currently done differently in different tools, as they are related to the internal data structures only without any standardisation.

2.2.3. Integration Capabilities

Beyond the already mentioned REST APIs, connection of OpenID compliant Identity Providers, and use of import/export with maDMPs, there are additional integration capabilities offered by the tools:

- Argos/OpenDMP provides integration with OpenAIRE; **DMP deposition** to Zenodo, CKAN, DSpace, and Dataverse; configurable API consumption and pre-filling of DMP contents via APIs.
- DAMAP specifies various **services to integrate other systems** with the DMP platform, typically CRIS. Recommended repositories and storages can be configured by populating database and DMP templates can be customised.
- DSW has **various integration points** that either allows to flexibly specify HTTP API call (request and response processing) or opens external service through JavaScript as pop-up implementing **DSW Integration SDK** (JavaScript library allowing to create Widgets, Importers, and Project Actions).

2.2.4. Expectations from Commons and Plans

Argos/OpenDMP, DAMAP, and DSW stated in their per-tool analyses that there should be formalisation and specification of an API with respect to maDMPs. Based on what the tools use and expect, using **OpenAPI specification** would be beneficial. Badging or

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>

simply a **mechanism to verify compliance** level or coverage of the specification could help enhancing and maintaining interoperability.

Aside from the machine-readable OpenAPI specification (incl. human-readable rendering e.g. via SwaggerUI), a **documentation for adopters** is necessary to cover basic principles, conventions, procedures, and it should include examples. However, such a documentation must be **well maintained and versioned** together with the specifications.

In terms of additional support, DAMAP mentions JavaScript library and Argos/OpenDMP native library in Java. While developing such libraries in all the used languages and technologies within platforms does not make sense, having OpenAPI specification may also help with this task by utilizing **automatic code generation** (e.g. Swagger Codegen).

2.3. DMP Platforms Interoperability

The analysis of DMP platforms—Argos (OpenDMP), DAMAP, and Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW)—along with contributions from DMPTuuli and Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO), revealed significant insights into their interoperability. These platforms use diverse programming languages and frameworks but share common data formats such as JSON for API communication. Most platforms (3 of 5 observed) offer REST APIs with OpenAPI specifications, facilitating seamless interaction. Authentication and authorization are typically managed through OpenID Connect, with API keys or tokens issued for non-human agents. Internal data models vary significantly, affecting how DMP-related information is captured, stored, and presented. However, all core tools adhere to the RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs.

These findings influence several key decisions for the OSTrails project. Implementing and adhering to OpenAPI specifications and prioritizing JSON for data exchange will enhance compatibility with existing platforms. Adopting OpenID Connect and API tokens will align with industry standards, facilitating easier integration. Designing flexible data models and emphasizing robust API integration will accommodate diverse DMP requirements and enhance the utility of the OSTrails platform. Additionally, developing comprehensive, versioned documentation and establishing a compliance verification process will support interoperability and adoption. To summarize:

- **Data Formats:** Common use of **JSON** for APIs, YAML for configuration, and document formats like DOCX or PDF for human-readable DMPs.
- **APIs: REST** (or at least HTTP/JSON-based) **APIs with OpenAPI specifications** (and SwaggerUI docs).
- **Authentication:** OpenID Connect, API keys, and tokens.
- **Data Models:** Varied internal models, adherence to **RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs**.
- **Integration:** Robust integration capabilities with services like SKGs, publication and data repositories, or CRIS.

- **Documentation:** Need for **comprehensive and versioned documentation, and compliance verification.**

2.4. Relation to OSTrails IF (M4)

We checked our analysis against the current OSTrails IF design (as described in the M4 document) in order to assess its level of compliance. The following list provides each point from the M4 report with an explanation of the current status or approach in each of the DMP tools, or possible solutions and suggestions:

1. **Exposing DMPs to (any) other services** – All three core DMP tools—Argos, DAMAP, and DSW—use REST/HTTP-based APIs and JSON format, which enable access to DMPs. To enhance this capability, it is essential to ensure that all tools have comprehensive and standardized API documentation using OpenAPI. Implementing common API endpoints for accessing single and multiple DMPs with filtering capabilities will facilitate consistent and efficient data sharing across different services.
2. **Notifying other services about “interesting changes” in DMPs** – Notification mechanisms are not currently implemented in the tools analysed. Therefore, designing and implementing an API to receive notifications and manage subscriptions is necessary. This includes defining a taxonomy of “interesting events” to standardize what changes should trigger notifications. The current solutions used in the tools can be extended to support this function, ensuring interoperability and timely updates to other services. However, the notifications should leverage the technologies and standards already used (RDA DMP Common Standard, JSON, REST / HTTP API).
3. **Consuming notifications about “DMP-related interesting changes” from other services** – Similar to the previous point, notification mechanisms for consuming updates from other services are not included in any of the analysed tools. Implementing a mechanism for receiving and processing notifications will require designing APIs that ensure consistency and interoperability. Adopting similar approaches to those used in notification APIs will help maintain uniformity and integration with external systems.
4. **Pushing DMPs to other services** – The analysed tools have different approaches to this pathway. Argos/OpenDMP integrate with OpenAIRE and allows DMP deposition to Zenodo, CKAN, DSpace, and Dataverse. DAMAP supports integration with various systems, typically CRIS, while DSW allows flexible HTTP API calls or JavaScript-based service integrations. Standardizing the method for exporting DMPs to repositories and other services using the maDMP format will ensure consistent and efficient data transfer.
5. **Allowing other services to contribute to DMPs (modify/create/populate)** – All core tools support some form of API for data manipulation. However, further enhancing these APIs to allow external services to contribute fully to DMPs is necessary. This includes defining robust permission models and common

authentication mechanisms, such as OpenID Connect, to securely manage access and contributions from various services, ensuring data integrity and security.

6. **Listing/searching records from other tools** – All core tools support integration with other services but lack standardized listing and searching methods. Developing endpoints for listing and searching records from external services (e.g., CRIS, databases) and standardizing the search and retrieval APIs will enable consistent access to external records. Aligning data schemas with existing ontologies and vocabularies, such as Schema.org, DCTerms, and DataCite, will further enhance interoperability and data sharing capabilities.

2.5. Identified Requirements

- DMP-R1. DMP IF *must* use RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-Actionable DMPs.
- DMP-R2. DMP IF *must* provide comprehensive, versioned documentation for API adopters. It *should* include basic principles, conventions, and examples to facilitate integration and ensure interoperability.
- DMP-R3. DMP IF *should* develop a RDA DMP Common Standard extension with respect to existing ontologies and vocabularies such as Schema.org, DCTerms, or DataCite.
- DMP-R4. DMP IF *should* specify API(s) using OpenAPI following REST architectural style. Such API(s) *should* use JSON as (one of) the supported file formats for communication and data exchange.
- DMP-R5. DMP IF *could* propose representation and exchange of DMPs in RDF or other semantically rich formats (while in alignment with RDA DMP Common Standard). In this sense, DMP IF *could* align data schemas with external ontologies and vocabularies, such as Schema.org, DCTerms, and DataCite, to enhance interoperability and support standardized data sharing practices across different platforms.
- DMP-R6. DMP IF *could* propose notification mechanism (from/to DMP Platforms) based on existing W3C recommendations (Web Notifications, Linked Data Notifications).
- DMP-R7. DMP IF *could* facilitate deeper integration with institutional systems like CRIS by specifying APIs and data models that are compatible with these environments. This *could* include predefined endpoints for data exchange and alignment with institutional workflows.
- DMP-R8. DMP IF *should* establish a compliance verification process or badging system to ensure that tools adhere to the OpenAPI specification and the RDA DMP Common Standard.

3. Scientific Knowledge Graphs

Science Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) are crucial to the OSTrails plan-track-assess framework, particularly in the **track** phase. SKGs facilitate continuous monitoring and organisation of diverse research objects, their relationships, ensuring their interoperability and data alignment. For the OSTrails project, an SKG is defined as any database/repository with information pertaining to research products, process and actors & agents which is able to present a graph type view on this information via a suitable API. Some of the tools covered in this part can be also seen as proto-SKGs (i.e. aim to fulfil the definition of SKG over the course of the project).

3.1. SKGs Included

The analysis included eight Science Knowledge Graphs. These SKGs were:

- **CESSDA Data Catalogue** (ID002, <https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu>) is a one-stop shop for European social science data, featuring metadata from CESSDA's Service Providers that include quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-mode data, both recent and historical. Study descriptions are available in their original languages, with about 75% provided in English, and some offered in both English and the local language.
- **International Virtual Observatory Alliance Registry (IVOA Registry)**, ID014, <http://rofr.ivoa.net>) enables users and applications to discover and select astrophysical resources, such as data and services, relevant to specific scientific problems. The IVOA Registry is a decentralized network of services that host and publish metadata collections and provide querying capabilities allowing users and client applications to discover resources to a full searchable registry.
- **Joint European Research Infrastructure of Coastal Observatories - Coastal Ocean Resource Environment (JERICO-CORE)**, ID022, <https://www.jerico-ri.eu/va-services/jerico-core/>) is the central hub for discovering, accessing, managing, and interacting with JERICO resources, including services, datasets, software, best practices, manuals, publications, organisations, projects, observatories, equipment, data servers, e-libraries, support, and training.
- **OpenAIRE Graph** (ID027, <https://graph.openaire.eu>) is a service that aggregates and curates metadata to populate a comprehensive and open collection of metadata on research outputs, projects, institutions, organisations, and researchers. By linking these entities, it unveils the intricate relationships and connections within the research world, creating a dynamic map of science across disciplines and geographic boundaries.
- **European Synchrotron Radiation Facility Data Portal (ESRF-DP)**, ID030, <https://data.esrf.fr>) stores all experimental data and corresponding metadata produced at the ESRF. It is based on flexible metadata catalogue solution for managing scientific metadata and data from a wide variety of domains following the FAIR data principles.

- **SOCIB KB** (ID040, <https://api.socib.es/home/>) is a resource catalogue, designed to streamline the assessment and management of SOCIB's assets. It facilitates the discoverability of assets to allow users to perform textual searches across the catalogue through the API. It aims to support advanced searches in SOCIB website, effectively connecting users to relevant data and other information associated with the organisation's assets.
- **SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOMP, ID044, <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu>)** is the discovery portal and entry point in the EOSC for SSH researchers, pooling and contextualizing resources such as tools, services, training materials, datasets, publications, and workflows.
- **Virtual Language Observatory (VLO, ID005, <https://vlo.clarin.eu/>)** is the central catalogue for the CLARIN RI for discovering language resources and interacting with language processing tools via the switchboard.

In the analysis, we incorporated insights from other national and thematic pilots, including LifeBlock (ID024).

3.2. Summary of Tools Analysis

In this section, we summarise the per-tool analyses of the Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and also put them into the context of similar tools within the European as well as global context.

3.2.1. Technologies and Standards

In the implementation of the observed Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), a diverse range of technologies and standards are utilized to manage and store data, as well as to ensure interoperability and data alignment across different platforms. This section delves into the common and unique technologies and standards used by different SKGs.

The technologies used by various SKGs include a mix of programming languages, frameworks, and storage solutions. Here are some of the key technologies:

- **Programming Languages and Frameworks:** SKGs use various programming languages for development: Java, Python, TypeScript, JavaScript, and others.
- **Data Storage Solutions:** The storage technologies vary across SKGs, incorporating relational databases, graph databases, or triple stores.

Despite the diversity in technologies, there is significant overlap in the standards used for data alignment. These standards ensure that data from different SKGs can be integrated and understood consistently. Below are some of the common standards and other interoperability means the SKGs that implement them:

- **Data formats**
 - **XML:** Utilized for instance by OA and ESRF-DP, typically with relation or in combination with OAI-PMH.

- **JSON**: employed by most of the SKGs (e.g. CESSDA, JERICO, SOCIB, SSHOMP, and ESRF-DP).
- **JSON-LD**: implemented with Schema.org or other schemas, e.g., by CESSDA and JERICO.
- **Data models and frameworks**
 - **DDI** (implemented in XML): Used intensively by CESSDA.
 - **NetCDF**: Used by SOCIB for data storage.
 - **SKG IF** (still in development and discussed in RDA): Being adopted by CESSDA (relaxed, in progress) and OpenAIRE (partly/planned), other communities are involved in the SKG-IF discussions and committed to the alignment in future.
 - **SKOS**: a preferred publication format for vocabularies and taxonomies
 - **CMDI**: an XML-based format that allows to model various metadata profiles build from reusable components adorned with concept links to add a common semantic overlay.
- **Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)**: Typical is **(re)use of existing PIDs** such as DOI (e.g. ESRF-DP), Handle, and URN/ARK (e.g. by CESSDA); others employ own specific identifiers in combination with external PIDs based on type/source (e.g. SSH Open Marketplace with internal and then attribute externalID).

Additionally, some SKGs use their own metadata classification systems and controlled vocabularies.

There are also examples of specific tools and standards used by different SKGs:

- IVOA/EURO-VO: Uses URIs, **OAI-PMH**, and **RegTAP**, with ongoing efforts to map to DCAT and Schema.org.
- OpenAIRE Graph: Mainly uses **JSON**, but also supports XML and CSV, and can ingest various custom formats through plugins.
- SSHOMP: Uses APIs with **JSON** and **various vocabularies** such as commonly used ISO 639-3 for languages, EOSC resource category list, and TaDiRAH 2 for Digital Humanities research activities.
- VLO: Uses SKOS-based vocabularies to add common semantics.
- ESRF-DP: Stores dataset metadata in using **ICAT**⁷ schemas (based on **CSMD**). Expose dataset metadata via **Datacite** DOI records.

In summary, while the implementation technologies of SKGs can vary widely, the adoption of common standards for data alignment ensures that these systems can effectively interoperate and integrate data from diverse sources. This shared use of standards like **JSON**, **XML**, and **PIDs** is crucial for maintaining the consistency and reliability of scientific data across different platforms. Also, it is visible that even plain JSON is not sufficient and related schemas or even a JSON-LD representation according to ontologies and vocabularies is the current aim.

⁷ <https://icatproject.org/user-documentation/icat-schema/>

3.2.2. Data Models and Operations

SKGs typically involve operations such as searching and ingestion which are crucial for the effective management and retrieval of scientific data. However, SKGs often store different types of entries and their attributes, and support additional operations based on their specific data models. The common operations are clearly:

- **Search:** Allows users to query the SKG collection for specific information.
- **Retrieval:** allow users to retrieve parts of the SKG graph with different granularity.
- **Ingestion:** The process of importing and storing data in the SKG collection via the underlying repositories and rich metadata catalogue, then reflected in the SKG.

Different SKGs use diverse data models to manage their specific types of entities, related attributes, semantic relationships, and operators on these. While the core entities are naturally identical or at least very similar in all SKGs (also with respect to the SKG IF), each SKG has its own custom concepts that also affect the operators (e.g. filtering, navigation through the graph, or ways of data entry/ingestion). The different SKGs also use various external schemas and models as template for their data models:

- CESSDA: Metadata is compliant with **SKG Interoperability Framework** (SKG IF). Harvests data from service providers using DDI, then converts harvested data to JSON and JSON-LD formats. Metadata is available in JSON via REST API, manually downloadable JSON, embedded JSON-LD (Schema.org), and via OAI-PMH endpoint as Dublin Core, DDI-C and DataCite. Controlled vocabularies/thesauri are used extensively for content description.
- IVOA/EURO-VO: Uses **VOResource** recommendations and extensions, which cover various aspects such as Identity, Curation, General Content, Coverage, and Access Information.
- JERICO: Implements **Dublin Core**, **DCAT**, and **Schema.org** for data modelling.
- OpenAIRE Graph: Utilizes a custom model with main entities such as Research product, data source, organisation, project, community, and person. Adheres to **OpenAIRE guidelines**, an application profile-based on **DataCite**, **JATS**, and **Dublin Core**, including integration of the COAR controlled vocabularies for repositories. Provides crosswalks for integrating data from non-compatible providers, ensuring a balance of flexibility, high quality, and interoperability standards.
- SOCIB: Employs a custom model with its own vocabularies⁸, categorizing data into products, platforms, instruments, and data sources.
- SSHOMP: Models tools and services, training materials, datasets, publications, and workflows, focusing on social sciences and humanities. Integrates various data sources and allows creation via a user interface.

⁸ more info in per-tool analysis

- ESRF-DP: **ICAT**⁹ schemas (based on CSMD¹⁰): comprising 27 entities, including core elements like investigations, datasets, and datafiles, along with instruments and parameters.
- VLO: CMDI metadata is harvested via OAI-PMH from the CLARIN metadata providers and next to being available in the faceted VLO browser, also made available as an SKG-IF compliant Linked Data graph using the CMD2RDF tooling. This graph is augmented with additional links to other SKGs using linksets created via the Lenticular Lens alignment tool.

Each SKG's data model is tailored to its specific requirements, balancing the need for flexibility, adherence to standards, and ensuring high-quality data management and interoperability.

3.2.3. Integration Capabilities

SKGs utilize various technologies to facilitate integration with other systems and provide access to their data and services. This section outlines the integration capabilities of different SKGs, highlighting the technologies they use and their specific implementations.

- **REST** (or at least similar HTTP-based) **API with OpenAPI/SwaggerUI**: Allows for the creation of web services that adhere to RESTful principles, with documentation provided by OpenAPI and SwaggerUI. Examples: CESSDA, JERICO, SOCIB, SSHOMP, or ESRF-DP.
- **OAI-PMH**: Enables the harvesting of metadata from different repositories. Examples: CESSDA, OpenAIRE Graph, ESRF-DP, or VLO. This can be used with different schemas, e.g. oai_datacite or oai_openaire.
- **SPARQL Endpoint**: Provides a query interface for retrieving data from RDF stores using the SPARQL query language. For example, available JERICO KG or VLO.
- **Graph API / Search API**: Specific to handling graph-based data models, providing advanced querying and search capabilities. For example, in OpenAIRE Graph or ESRF-DP (instead of or in addition to the SPARQL endpoint).
- **OAuth 2.0 / OpenID Connect**: Standards for authentication and authorization used for private access, integrations as SSO, or creating/editing records (e.g. OpenAIRE Graph or ESRF).
- **RegTAP** (Registry Interface for VO Resources): Connectors using web API, no authentication required for reading; creation/updating may require authentication; used for instance in IVOA/EURO-VO.

SKGs use various integration technologies such as **APIs with OpenAPI/SwaggerUI, OAI-PMH for metadata harvesting and re-harvesting, SPARQL endpoints, Graph APIs**, and standards like **OAuth 2.0/OpenID Connect** for secure authentication and authorization. Typically, SKGs offer some open access parts that do not require authentication or use simple methods like HTTP Basic Auth or API keys, exemplified by

⁹ <https://icatproject.org/user-documentation/icat-schema/>

¹⁰ as described in per-tool analysis document

JERICO and SOCIB. For more sensitive operations or access to private records, SKGs such as OpenAIRE Graph and ESRF implement OAuth 2.0/OpenID Connect to ensure secure access. These integration capabilities are crucial for maintaining interoperability and enabling effective interaction with external systems.

3.2.4. Expectations from Commons and Plans

There are different specific expectations and plans for integration with broader scientific commons to enhance their interoperability, data quality, and functionality; however, several overlaps and key points stand out.

For instance, CESSDA is focusing on using validation via profiles and schemas, alongside **source code badging with SQAaaS**. They plan to **incorporate more persistent identifiers** such as ORCID and ROR, and to implement the **SKG Interoperability Framework (SKG IF)**. Similarly, JERICO aims to improve interoperability with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and adjust its model to align with OSTrails, though they are not yet assessing but are open to implementing these standards.

The OpenAIRE Graph is working on exporting the SKG collection via the **SKG IF**, including **JSON-LD to ensure improved data structuring** and alignment by using widely adopted controlled vocabularies and schemas.

SOCIB, while not currently integrated with Commons, is open to changes needed to improve interoperability as required. SSHOMP has clear plans to define interfaces using **OpenAPI specifications and enable symmetric exchanges** between catalogues, such as SSHOMP and OpenAIRE Graph. They aim to enrich these exchanges with **new entities, incorporate Data Management Plans (DMPs)**, and elevate workflows to first-class citizens within their system.

ESRF is focused on improving dataset metadata quality with community topic terms (Photon and Neutrons Experimental Technique, PaNET¹¹ vocabulary) and dataset publication citations (via integration with PUMA ID032 software). The ESRF also aims at improving interoperability with DMPs through **standard APIs for updating and retrieving DMP-related entities** (datasets, grants, projects...) via the SKG IF.

IVOA is working with XML-based standards and is progressing towards **implementing OpenAPI and SKG IF**. These efforts highlight the commitment of SKGs to evolve and adapt their systems for seamless integration and enhanced collaboration within the broader scientific commons.

CLARIN is focused on making its joint metadata domain available through the VLO also available via the **SKG Interoperability Framework (SKG IF)** and improve the interoperability by alignment with key entities from other SKGs.

¹¹ <https://github.com/ExPaNDS-eu/ExPaNDS-experimental-techniques-ontology>

3.3. SKGs Interoperability

As expected, from the per-tool analyses, we see that interoperability is a crucial aspect for the effective integration of Scientific Knowledge Graphs with broader scientific commons. The following key points and considerations can guide design and implementation decisions to enhance SKG interoperability:

- **Data Models and Alignment:** Adjusting data models to **align with common standards like DublinCore, DataCite, or Schema.org**; and the use of JSON-LD can enhance compatibility. OpenAIRE Graph supports the **OpenAIRE Guidelines and** crosswalks to the **SKG IF**, to export data via JSON(-LD) or XML, to improve data structuring and alignment. Aligning data models with widely accepted standards ensures smoother data exchange and integration. In collaboration with the RDA SKG-IF WG the SKG-IF will be modified and extended to fit any new requirements from the new community SKGs. Another necessary alignment effort is between the different overlapping vocabularies, efforts exist or are underway in other projects to facilitate mappings between such vocabularies.
- **Standardization and Validation:** Implementing standardized validation processes and adhering to established profiles and schemas are essential. For example, CESSDA uses validation via profiles and schemas, and plans to implement SKG IF. Adopting similar standards can ensure data consistency and quality across different SKGs.
- **Improving interoperability between SKGs via APIs:** Clearly defining APIs and interfaces using **specifications like OpenAPI is vital**. SSHOMP plans to define interfaces using OpenAPI specs to enable symmetric exchanges between catalogues. Providing well-documented and standardized APIs can facilitate easier integration and interaction with other systems.
- **Persistent Identifiers:** Incorporating persistent identifiers such as ORCID, ROR, DOI, and Handle improves traceability and reliability of data. CESSDA plans to add more persistent identifiers to enhance data management. Ensuring the use of persistent identifiers can improve the **robustness of data referencing across SKGs**.
- **Compliance with Existing Interoperability Frameworks:** Ensuring compatibility with interoperability frameworks like the ones published under the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) domain can expand the reach and usability of SKGs. JERICO aims to improve interoperability with EOSC. Integrating with established frameworks can provide broader access to data and facilitate collaboration.
- **Alignment for Authentication and Security:** Utilizing secure authentication (if needed) methods like **OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect** ensures data security while enabling access control. By aligning and using standardized solution enhances the interoperability for inter-tools communication. OpenAIRE Graph and ESRF-DP use OAuth 2.0/OpenID Connect for secure access. Implementing robust authentication mechanisms protects data integrity and privacy.

By focusing on these key points, designers and implementers can enhance the interoperability of SKGs, ensuring they can effectively integrate with broader scientific commons and facilitate collaborative research efforts. Standardization, clear interface definitions, use of persistent identifiers, alignment with common data models, compatibility with existing frameworks, and robust authentication are essential components of a successful SKG interoperability strategy.

3.4. Relation to OSTrails IF (M4)

To analyse compliance with the OSTrails IF, as described in the M4 report, and subsequently their functions, we compared our analysis against it. The following list details each point from the M4 report, along with an explanation of the current status or approach in each of the SKG tools, or possible solutions and suggestions.

1. **Support access to metadata and links in SKGs from other services (random access to single SKG record, query SKG to get a collection of record, resolve ID by relationship type to get related records)** - SKGs employ various integration solutions and technologies. Some tools use REST APIs with OpenAPI/SwaggerUI documentation for accessing SKG, while others use OAI-PMH for harvesting metadata from different repositories or SPARQL endpoints for retrieving data from RDF stores. To resolve relationships to access related records, SKG tools use different metadata taxonomies and vocabularies that are either standard and widely accepted (e.g., JERICO uses Dublin Core and DCAT) or entirely custom. For instance, the OpenAIRE Graph employs its own internal data model but implements crosswalks for integration with standards and third-party data models. Therefore, ensuring that all tools are compatible by using common vocabularies and standards or providing mappings and crosswalks is essential.
2. **Notifying other services about “interesting events” regarding records in SKGs** - Notification mechanisms are currently not implemented in the analysed SKG tools. Therefore, designing and implementing an API to receive notifications and manage subscriptions is necessary. This includes defining a taxonomy of "interesting events" to standardize which changes should trigger notifications. The existing solutions used in the tools can be extended to support this function, ensuring interoperability and timely updates to other services. The notifications should leverage the technologies and standards already used.
3. **Allowing other services to contribute to SKGs (modify/create)** - Allowing other services to contribute to SKGs involves implementing a common API and defining robust permission models as well as common authentication and authorization mechanisms, such as OpenID Connect/OAuth 2.0. These mechanisms, already used by OpenAIRE Graph and ESRF, can securely manage access and contributions from various services, ensuring data integrity and security. Design of the API for contributing (or triggering ingestion) is needed first for further technological choices.

3.5. Identified Requirements

- SKG-R1. SKG IF *must* support common data formats and standards like JSON, XML, and JSON-LD to ensure interoperability and data integration across various SKGs following the RDA SKG IF specification (and eventually extend it or contribute to it).
- SKG-R2. SKG IF *should* design robust API(s) (e.g., REST, SPARQL) and API documentation using OpenAPI/SwaggerUI, allowing external services to query, retrieve, and ingest data. This will enhance integration with other scientific tools and platforms.
- SKG-R3. SKG IF *must* align with persistent identifier (PID) systems such as DOI, ORCID, and ROR for improved data traceability, attribution, and reliability across SKGs.
- SKG-R4. SKG IF *could* facilitate crosswalks between different data models used by various SKGs, ensuring compatibility and integration even when custom models are used. This could include mappings between internal and external schemas like Dublin Core or DataCite.
- SKG-R5. SKG IF *should* specify a common secure authentication and authorization mechanisms such as OAuth 2.0/OpenID Connect for managing access to data, particularly for sensitive operations like modifying or contributing records (i.e. for cases where open access is not possible).
- SKG-R6. SKG IF *should* specify standards for metadata harvesting using protocols like OAI-PMH, enabling SKGs to easily aggregate and share metadata across different repositories, improving data accessibility and discoverability.
- SKG-R7. SKG IF *could* enable event notifications for external services, allowing them to subscribe to changes or updates in SKG records through APIs. This will ensure timely updates and interactions between SKGs and external services.
- SKG-R8. SKG IF *should* support validation and schema compliance mechanisms to ensure high data quality and alignment with international standards such as EOSC, enhancing the reliability and consistency of scientific data across platforms.

4. FAIR Assessment Tools

FAIR Assessment tools are crucial to the OSTrails plan-track-assess framework, particularly in the **assess** phase. These tools deliver modular and extendable FAIR tests, making the metrics machine-actionable (maFAIRTest) and providing user guidance. They can be implemented or reused in different tools that assist at any stage of the research lifecycle ensuring good practices of FAIR.

4.1. FAIR Assessment Tools Included

The analysis included eight FAIR assessment tools. These tools were:

- **CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV)**, ID006, (<https://cmv.cessda.eu>) validates DDI metadata records used by CESSDA's tools and services, against a given DDI Profile. Designed to be versatile, CMV can also validate records against any DDI Profile, making it applicable for a wide range of other uses.
- **FAIR-Aware** (ID015, <https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl>) is an online tool that assists researchers and data managers in assessing their understanding of FAIR requirements before uploading datasets to a repository. It features 10 well-designed questions, supplemented by additional questions on implementation likelihood, and provides practical tips and information to enhance users' comprehension of FAIR principles.
- **FAIR Evaluator** (alt/new: **FAIR Champion**, ID016, <https://w3id.org/AmlFAIR>) is a self-assessment Web application for evaluating the degree to which a Web-accessible digital object adheres to the core FAIR Principles by executing one or more of its 25 tests. It is currently being replaced by a new iteration named FAIR Champion, following recommendations from the EOSC Task force on FAIR Metrics and Data Quality.
- **FAIR Validator** (ID017, <https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.validator>) is a FAIR Assessment Service for Research Products, that is integrated into the OpenAIRE Validator and aligned with the OpenAIRE Guidelines.
- **FAIR Research Objects Assessment (FAIROS)**, ID018, (<https://w3id.org/FAIROS>) is a FAIR assessment service for Research Objects integrated with the ROHub platform. FAIROs relies on FAIR assessment services such as F-UJI (for datasets) to further assess the FAIRness of the elements included in a Research Object.
- **Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR (FOOPS!)**, ID020: (<https://w3id.org/foops/>) is a web application for assessing the FAIRness level for ontologies and vocabularies developed from many domains.
- **IVOA Services Validation** (ID021, <https://voparis-validation-reports.obspm.fr>) is a reporting web application designed to collect and present statistics on the conformance validation of IVOA Data Access Layer (DAL) services.
- **PADC Validator** (ID029, <http://voparis-validator.obspm.fr>) is a web-based validator to evaluate conformance of astrophysical data access services with the

IVOA standards, including VOTable, Simple Cone Search, Simple Image Access (v1 and v2), Simple Spectral Access, TAP, and HiPS.

In the analysis, we also considered inputs from other national and thematic pilots, such as the EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (ID080), F-UJI (ID083) and the CLARIN Curation Dashboard (ID004).

4.2. Summary of Tools Analysis

This section encapsulates the evaluations of various tools, offering a concise synthesis of their functionalities, strengths, and limitations. This section distils the per-tool analyses to provide an overarching understanding of each tool's performance and suitability for different applications.

4.2.1. Technologies and Standards

Programming languages and related technologies employed in the evaluation tools are quite diverse, spanning from Java, Python, Ruby, PHP, JavaScript, to TypeScript. Despite this diversity, there are certain overlaps specific to FAIR evaluation and related best practices that ensure consistency and reliability across tools.

The evaluation of compliance with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles relies on a variety of technologies and standards. Below is a list of these technologies with brief descriptions and examples of FAIR assessment services that use them.

- **JSON/YAML:** Lightweight data-interchange formats that are easy for humans to read and write, and easy for machines to parse and generate. JSON and YAML are frequently interchangeable, for example, in the case of the OpenAPI specification of Web Service interfaces, where both YAML and JSON representations of the interface metadata are acceptable. Various tools use JSON and/or YAML to output validation results (for instance: CMV, FAIR Evaluator, FAIR Validator, FAIROS, FOOPS!, IVOA, F-UJI). Moreover, some also use it for inputs or intermediary representations, e.g. for inter-service communication or configuration.
- **XML:** A markup language that defines rules for encoding documents in a format that is both human- and machine-readable. Sometimes it is also used to present results (e.g. PADC Validator) or in combination with OAI-PMH (e.g. in case of the FAIR Validator). CMV also validates DDI XML files using XSD files (also XML-related technology).
- **RDF/OWL:** RDF is a framework for the representation and exchange of graph data. OWL is a description logic that can be used to create classification systems through its explicit definitions of concepts, often based on their properties. On the Web, OWL is used to provide a layer of interpretation over RDF graphs. FOOPS! and the FAIR Champion use RDF/OWL to promote adherence to widely used metadata schemas such as Dublin Core, FOAF, and Schema.org.

- **JSON-LD:** A method of encoding RDF/OWL into JSON. Used to promote interoperability of outputs, for instance, in FAIR Evaluator or FAIROS; with use of standard ontologies and vocabularies (e.g. Schema.org).
- **RO-Crates:** A community-driven data packaging format that encapsulates research data with its metadata and relationships. FAIROS uses RO-Crates encoded in JSON-LD adjusted for F-UJI and FOOPS! to output results in JSON.

These technologies and standards form the backbone of various FAIR assessment services, ensuring that data and metadata are handled in a structured, consistent, and interoperable manner.

4.2.2. Data Models and Operations

The FAIR assessment tools share several common aspects in their data models and operations. Understanding these overlaps can provide insights into how these tools evaluate FAIR principles and process data. Here is a summary highlighting the commonalities and examples from specific tools.

- **URI-Based Input:** Most of tools use URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers) to reference and validate specific resources or metadata. CMV utilizes document URI and profile URI to validate documents against profiles. FAIR Evaluator accepts URIs of metadata records and test collections to conduct evaluations. FOOPS! processes URIs of RDF/OWL vocabularies in various RDF formats for evaluation.
- **Validation and Assessment:** Tools often validate or assess resources based on predefined rules or criteria, producing detailed results, such as scores or feedback. FAIR Validator applies rules to verify whether metadata records of publications, data, and software (compatible with OpenAIRE guidelines) comply to the FAIR Maturity Group criteria; as a response it generates compliance results and feedback on the failing rules. FAIR Evaluator and F-UJI assessments are primarily (though not entirely) aligned with the requirements defined by the RDA FAIR Maturity Model. PADC Validator validates resources and produces XHTML/XML bases of the tests. FAIROS and FOOPS! Assess specific types of resources (ontologies/vocabularies and Research Objects) adapting the FAIR principles accordingly.
- **Results Aggregation and Reporting:** Tools aggregate results from various assessments or validations and present them in a structured format. FAIROS dispatches Research Objects to appropriate tools based on type, then aggregates and presents results. FOOPS! F-UJI, and the FAIR Evaluator aggregate results from multiple individual tests on RDF/OWL vocabularies and provides a JSON summary with a visualization, scores and checks. FAIR-Aware collects responses to questions and provides guidance based on FAIR principles, presenting results based on aggregated responses.
- **Structured Data and Metadata Handling:** Tools handle data and metadata in structured formats, often using JSON, XML, or RDF. FAIR Evaluator and FOOPS! use JSON to describe the results of tests, including scores and logs. FAIROS outputs

results in JSON format, integrating data from various assessment tools. IVOA Services Validation maintains a relational database with structured information about services, errors, and test queries.

- **Question and Answer-Based Assessment:** Some tools evaluate FAIRness by asking users structured questions and analysing responses (user-based inputs). FAIR-Aware uses a set of structured questions and answers based on FAIR guiding principles to provide evaluation of users' understanding of these principles along with further information serving as a training tool.

These commonalities in approaches across different FAIR assessment tools highlight a shared focus on structured, URI-based inputs, detailed validation processes, and comprehensive result aggregation. By leveraging these overlaps, tools can be integrated ensure consistent and effective evaluation of FAIR principles.

4.2.3. Integration Capabilities

FAIR assessment tools offer different integration capabilities, from APIs and documentation to authentication methods. Here is a summary of how these tools handle integration and connectivity:

- **APIs and Documentation:** Most tools provide APIs for integration, with varying levels of documentation and support. CMV, FAIROs and F-UJI features a **REST-like API with OpenAPI/SwaggerUI** for public use, including developer documentation and links to profiles. FAIR Evaluator offers an HTTP API with partial OpenAPI specifications and a README file detailing the API, and additionally publishes all of its individual tests as independent tools with their own OpenAPI definitions. FAIR Validator provides a REST API with OpenAPI specs, integrates with other OpenAIRE tools using AAI (if not open access).
- **Authentication and Access:** Tools vary in their authentication requirements, with some offering open access while others **use tokens or credentials**. FAIR-Aware has open access with CSV export capabilities; trainers receive credentials for result access, but no API is provided. FAIROs uses a REST API with SwaggerHub and OpenAPI and integrates with other tools, requiring a service token issued by the developer team. FOOPS! and the FAIR Evaluator provide HTTP APIs that support POST requests with no authentication required.
- **Integration with Other Tools:** Some tools are designed to integrate with other services, enhancing their functionality and interoperability. FAIROs is integrated with FOOPS, F-UJI, and SOMEF, utilizing a REST API with OpenAPI and SwaggerHub for seamless operation. PADC Validator on the other hand is not designed for direct integration but is used by IVOA Services Validation for its validation process.
- **Export and Standalone Functionality:** Certain tools focus on exporting data or operate as standalone applications without API support. For example, FAIR-Aware functions as a standalone app with CSV export and open access; no API is available (as not identified suitable for the use cases). Others usually allow to export or retrieve JSON or JSON-LD result for further processing.

These integration capabilities reflect a range of approaches from open APIs and detailed documentation to varying levels of authentication and integration with other tools. This diversity allows users to choose tools that best fit their needs for connectivity and functionality.

4.2.4. Expectations from Commons and Plans

The FAIR assessment tools collectively aim to **enhance interoperability and integration by adopting common standards** and incorporating various systems. Many tools focus on improving how they interact with other systems, which includes following standardized schemas, integrating with additional tools, and refining their integration processes to align with shared specifications. This collaborative approach is intended to streamline the evaluation process and facilitate better interaction across different platforms.

Another key area of focus is the **standardization of output formats** and data handling practices. Tools like FOOPS! FAIR Champion, and FAIROS are leading efforts to **adopt common specifications for test results** and use JSON-LD for outputs. This standardization is crucial for ensuring that results are consistent and compatible, making it easier to compare and integrate data from different sources.

Finally, tools are working on enhancing their functional capabilities and flexibility. This includes **validating specifications, improving metadata extraction, and supporting additional formats**. For instance, CMV plans to extend its validation to include checking contents and structures against FAIR baselines. These enhancements aim to provide more robust and versatile solutions for FAIR assessment, accommodating a broader range of needs and use cases.

4.3. FAIR Assessment Tools Interoperability

Interoperability among FAIR assessment tools is essential to enhance the effectiveness and cohesion of data evaluation processes. A major area of overlap is the adoption of **common APIs and data formats**. Many tools utilize **REST APIs and standardized formats like JSON and JSON-LD for outputs**. This closer alignment in data handling and communication methods should facilitate seamless integration and data exchange, ensuring consistent and interoperable evaluation results across different systems. Use of the **OpenAPI specification** (or other similar tools) is common and can also be considered for the standardization.

Adopting common schemas and models is another critical factor to achieve interoperability. By developing and adhering to **shared schemas/models, tools can ensure compatibility and ease of integration**. This standardization supports reliable data comparisons and enables more comprehensive analyses when aggregating results

from multiple sources, providing a **unified framework for evaluating compliance** with the FAIR principles.

Integrability and the **aggregation of test results** are also key to improve the overall functionality. The capability to dispatch data to appropriate tools and aggregate results enhances the depth and breadth of FAIR evaluations. This approach allows for a holistic view of data compliance and supports more thorough **assessments by combining outputs from various evaluation tests or tools that may examine slightly different facets of a digital object, or similar facets from the perspective of different expert communities.**

Advancing interoperability involves focusing on common schemas, APIs, and data formats, as well as improving integration and aggregation capabilities. By addressing these areas, tools can provide more effective and cohesive FAIR assessments, contributing to improved data management practices and more **consistent and reproducible evaluations of data findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.**

4.4. Relation to OSTrails IF (M4)

To assess compliance with the OSTrails IF as outlined in the M4 report, we compared our analysis against the criteria specified. The following list details each point from the M4 report, along with an explanation of the current status or approach in FAIR assessment tools and provides possible solutions and suggestions for improvement.

1. **Metadata Exposure and test execution** – Most FAIR assessment tools offer APIs for integration, but they often use different approaches. Therefore, it would be beneficial to implement standardized API endpoints for exposing metadata related to various elements of FAIR assessment tools, such as test implementations, FAIR metrics, and FAIR benchmarks. Additionally, these endpoints should support initiating tests or algorithm executions and include documentation in a specification like OpenAPI. If authentication and authorization is necessary, it is also advisable to implement common mechanisms, such as OpenID Connect/OAuth 2.0, to control access to test metadata and execution of tests or algorithms.
2. **Develop a data model and exchange formats for exchanging test results and test set results, tests, metrics and benchmarks** - Currently, FAIR assessment tools use a variety of formats for exchanging data, including JSON, JSON-LD, XML, and RDF/OWL. While JSON is commonly used for its simplicity and ease of integration, XML is utilized by some tools for its structured and verbose nature, and RDF/OWL formats are employed for their semantic richness and interoperability. To enhance consistency and interoperability across tools, a standardized data model should be developed that can be used to harmonize over these formats (either by the assessment tool authors adopting the suggested shared format, or by defining mappings from the various output formats into the shared one). By defining a unified schema for test results, test set results, tests,

metrics, and benchmarks, and ensuring compatibility with JSON, JSON-LD, XML, and RDF/OWL, data exchange between diverse FAIR assessment tools can be streamlined and made more efficient.

3. **Governance of tests, test implementations and metrics** - One of the requirements from the OSTrails Interoperability Framework (Milestone 4) for FAIR assessment tools is the establishment of a governance process for incorporating tests, test implementations, and metrics into the OSTrails Commons to ensure their consistency and quality. The current analysed FAIR assessment tools do not specify whether they have such governance processes for including externally authored tests, test implementations, or metrics. This lack of clarity necessitates the development of a standardized governance framework to maintain high standards and facilitate the seamless integration of contributions from various authors.

4.5. Identified Requirements

- FAIR-R1. FAIR IF *must* specify standardized API endpoints (e.g., OpenAPI) for exposing metadata related to FAIR assessments and initiating tests or algorithms.
- FAIR-R2. FAIR IF *should* bring a data model for exchanging test specifications, test results, metrics, and benchmarks including related metadata.
- FAIR-R3. FAIR IF *should* establish a governance framework to ensure consistency and quality in tests, test implementations, and metrics across various FAIR assessment tools.
- FAIR-R4. FAIR IF *should* ensure that tools aggregate and report results in a standardized format (e.g., JSON-LD), allowing seamless integration of outputs from different assessments.
- FAIR-R5. FAIR IF *could* promote interoperability by adopting common schemas and formats (e.g., JSON or RDF formats), enhancing data compatibility and exchange between diverse tools.
- FAIR-R6. FAIR IF *should* allow to verify compliance with its specifications to ensure that assessment tools and services align.

5. Other Supporting Tools

Other tools (services and resources) support the entire OSTrails plan-track-assess framework. This includes Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) and Repositories. These tools can be integrated with Science Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and FAIR assessment tools to ensure data interconnection and the retrieval of test results. They can also store data related to Data Management Plans (DMPs), facilitating effective data management.

5.1. Other Supporting Tools Included

The analysis included 19 tools categorized as “others” in our classification. These tools included:

- **CESSDA – The European Language Social Science Thesaurus (CESSDA ELSST, ID003, <https://thesauri.cessda.eu>)** is a comprehensive, multilingual thesaurus for the social sciences, encompassing over 3,300 concepts across disciplines such as politics, sociology, economics, education, law, crime, demography, health, employment, ICT, and environmental science. Used for data discovery within CESSDA, ELSST facilitates access to data resources across Europe, regardless of domain, resource, language, or vocabulary.
- **Croatian Research Information Systems (CroRIS, ID007, <https://www.croris.hr>)** is a national information system providing comprehensive and reliable data on Croatia's scientific and research ecosystem. Supporting open science and transparency, CroRIS features a modular design based on the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) data model, managing entities such as persons, organisational units, projects, publications, events, equipment, patents, and products.
- **CESSDA Vocabulary Service (CVS, ID008, <https://vocabularies.cessda.eu>)** allows users to discover, browse, and download controlled vocabularies in various languages, available in SKOS, HTML, and PDF formats. It also includes an Editor for authorized users to create, manage, and translate vocabularies, with access granted by the user management team, and can be used for in-house vocabularies of other agencies.
- **FAIRSharing (ID019, <https://fairsharing.org>)** is an informative and educational resource that serves as both a repository of metadata on data and metadata standards, policies, and databases, and a knowledge graph showing their interrelations. It illustrates how standards are implemented, how databases exchange data, and how standards and terminologies are interconnected.
- **Lenticular Lens (ID023, <https://lenticularlens.org>)** is a tool for constructing link sets between entities from different datasets, tracking alignment configurations and algorithms, and reporting on manual corrections and validations. As a domain-agnostic tool, it reuses existing matching approaches to address user-dependent and context-specific link discovery, explicit concept mapping,

integration of multiple datasets, combining entity matching algorithms, structure-based evaluation, visual validation support, and metadata documentation for reproducibility.

- **OpenAIRE Broker** (ID026, <http://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.broker>) intermediates between data sources contributing to the OpenAIRE Graph (e.g. repositories, publishers, aggregators) and the OpenAIRE Graph, facilitating metadata exchange with the aim of enriching data source metadata collections to enhance repository content quality and discoverability. Key functionalities include notifications of metadata enrichment to data sources, discoverability of notifications to content to identify the necessary subscriptions and streamlined integration options via manual review or API access (for DSpace platforms), identifying missing or additional metadata values like PIDs, project links, ORCID IDs, subject classifications, abstracts, publication dates, other versions, and related works.
- **OpenOrgs** (ID028, <https://openorgs.openaire.eu>) is a data curation tool designed to enhance the accuracy and visibility of research organisations in the OpenAIRE Graph and across OpenAIRE portals by reduplicating metadata records collected from different organisations registries (e.g. CORDIS portal, ROR.org, ROAR). The tool suggests potential duplicates to data curators, who can merge (and “unmerge”) records and refine and enhance metadata. It ensures precise, clear organisational records, thereby improving the discoverability of research outputs and facilitating compliance with open access mandates.
- **RCAAP** (ID033, <https://www.rcaap.pt>) aggregates and indexes Open Access research products from Portuguese institutional repositories, providing a unified platform for searching and discovering thousands of scholarly publications and research data, including journal articles, conference papers, theses, dissertations and datasets.
- **RECOLECTA** (ID0035, <https://recolecta.fecyt.es/>) is the national harvester for open access repositories in Spain, focused on facilitating metadata interoperability at the national level and providing with access, visibility and impact to scientific research outputs. It provides the following services to the national community of open access repositories: metadata validation; metadata enrichment; quality assessment, harvesting; usage statistics; and a search engine.
- **ROHub** (ID037, <https://www.rohub.org>) is a comprehensive platform for storing, managing, and preserving scientific investigations via Research Objects, enabling publication, discovery, and reuse of scientific knowledge with DOIs. It supports data integrity using the RO-Crate specification for research object serialization and integrates with various EOSC services and external tools. ROHub provides a REST API, web portal, and Python library for managing research objects, supporting FAIR and open science principles.
- **Software Heritage** (ID041, <https://www.softwareheritage.org>) is the universal software source code archive, aiming to collect, preserve, and share all publicly available source code, enabling applications across cultural heritage, industry, and research. Key features include long-term access to source code and its full

development history, viewing revision history, downloading directories and generating unique identifiers (SWHIDs).

- **SOMEF** (ID042, <https://github.com/KnowledgeCaptureAndDiscovery/somef>) is a command line interface for automatically extracting relevant metadata from code repositories (readme, configuration files, documentation, etc.)
- **SSH Data Citation Service** (ID043, <https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/>) is a software tool that aggregates and analyses metadata related to a citation from various sources, providing a unified view and functionalities to assess metadata actionability and interoperability.
- **SSH Vocabulary Commons** (ID045, <https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu>) is a suite of services that supports users in the creation, publication, and maintenance of controlled vocabularies. It includes tools such as Vocabs browse, which allows exploration of published vocabularies, and Vocabs editor for collaborative editing based on the SKOS data model. The platform also offers an API for programmatic access to vocabularies and employs tools like Skosify and qSKOS for quality assessment and improvement.
- **CESSDA Metadata Aggregator** (ID048, <https://cessda-metadata-aggregator.readthedocs.io>) provides an OAI-PMH endpoint for the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC). The CDC hosts metadata for over 40,000 data collections curated by CESSDA's Service Providers (SPs) across 20 European countries and, in this role, serves as an intermediary for other aggregators, including the OpenAIRE Graph, BASE, GoTriple, and B2Find.
- **Digital Academic Archives and Repositories (Dabar)**, (ID049, <https://dabar.srce.hr>) is a Croatian national e-infrastructure that simplifies the implementation and maintenance of interoperable institutional and thematic repositories, currently hosting over 175 digital repositories. Dabar includes a variety of content such as thesis, publications, research data, and Data Management Plans.
- **TU Wien Research Data Repository (TUWRD)**, (ID060, <https://researchdata.tuwien.at>) is TU Wien's institutional repository that enables researchers to store, share, and publish research data, adhering to the FAIR principles for data management. TUWRD is based on the open-source InvenioRDM platform that powers Zenodo.
- **Data Repository of the University of Minho (DataRepositóriUM)**, (ID068, <https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt>) is the Institutional Data Repository for sharing, publishing, and managing research data, adhering to General Dataverse Community Norms and supporting compliance with funder requirements. DataRepositóriUM allows the deposit, preservation, and citation of data in various formats. It is registered in global repositories registries like re3data.org and FAIRsharing and delivers records to the OpenAIRE Graph by compatibility with the OpenAIRE guidelines.
- **OPUS CTA Provenance** (ID088, <https://voparis-uws-test.obspm.fr>) is a job manager that follows the Universal Worker System pattern v1.1 (UWS) as defined by the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA), and that also captures and exposes the provenance information of jobs and results

In the analysis, we also integrated inputs from various national and thematic pilots, including the Digital Archive of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts (DAIS, ID056), Central Repository (CeR, ID057), CHEmistry RepositoRY (Cherry, ID058), Vinca Repository (VinaR, ID059), Phaidra Repository (PHAIDRA, ID061), The Austrian Social Science Data Archive (AUSSDA, ID062), Polen FCT-FCCN national data repository (ID069), French Open Science Monitor (ID070), the HAL national repository (ID071), eNauka (ID012), PT CRIS framework and Ciencia Vitae CV platform (PT CRIS, ID031), Publication and User Experiment Metadata Analyser (PUMA, ID032), Research Finland CSC (ID036), SweCRIS (ID047), and TU Graz Repository (ID063).

5.2. Summary of Tools Analysis

In this section, we summarize key findings from our per-tool analyses of various other supporting tools. Unlike the previous sections focused on DMP platforms, SKGs, and FAIR Assessment tools, we now further categorize the other supporting tools into two subgroups: CRIS (Current Research Information Systems) and repositories. These two subgroups were identified as particularly significant in terms of the numerical representation, with other tools falling into an additional category for miscellaneous analysis.

5.2.1. Current Research Information Systems

CroRIS (Croatian Research Information System) is a notable example within the CRIS category and as the only CRIS representative prepared the per-tool analysis. It provides comprehensive data on the scientific and research ecosystem in Croatia. Its modular design, based on the CERIF data model, effectively manages and disseminates research information, supporting open science, transparency, and public availability of Croatian research activities.

In addition to other CRIS mentioned in the previous section, we also examined additional CRIS systems like IRINS¹², Pure¹³, or CRIS¹⁴ (based on DRIS – the Directory of Research Information Systems, <https://eurocris.org/services/dris>), which similarly support comprehensive research information management and interoperability. All above mentioned systems above offer detailed researcher profiles, integrate with institutional repositories, and emphasize national-level research information management. For instance, SweCRIS is known for its integration with national funding bodies, enhancing the visibility and accessibility of research data.

- **Data Models:** CroRIS is structured around the CERIF model, a temporal, multilingual, relational data model encompassing entities such as institutions,

¹² <https://irins.org/irins/>

¹³ <https://www.elsevier.com/products/pure>

¹⁴ <https://www.cristin.no/english/>

persons, projects, research results, and publications. This model is extended to include additional entities for comprehensive data management.

- **Standards and Recommendations:** CroRIS aligns its metadata with the OAI-PMH protocol to ensure standardized data representation and interoperability with the OpenAIRE Graph (OpenAIRE CRIS guidelines) and other open access systems. The Equipment and Services module adheres to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) metadata requirements.
- **Data Exchange Formats:** XML is used for **OAI-PMH** to facilitate metadata harvesting and integration with other systems, while JSON is employed for APIs, providing a lightweight data interchange format for seamless data exchange.
- **Authentication and Authorization:** CroRIS utilizes AAI@EduHr for secure and standardized user authentication, and implements role-based access control, defining roles such as Superadmin, CroRIS Coordinator, Module Editors, and Basic Users to manage access levels.
- **Integration Capabilities:** CroRIS offers APIs for data on institutions, scientists, projects, equipment, publications, journals, and events. Most APIs are publicly accessible, with some requiring authorized access. The APIs are REST-based with detailed documentation, facilitating data extraction and integration. Other widely used CRIS/RIMS also tend to offer **HTTP/REST APIs** either documented in form of human-readable dev documentation and/or **OpenAPI specification**. OAI-PMH is traditionally used for data harvesting.

According to DRIS, many institutions continue to develop their own CRIS (Current Research Information Systems) tailored to their specific needs. While these bespoke systems offer the advantage of customization to address unique institutional requirements and workflows, they also present significant challenges, particularly in terms of interoperability. Custom-built CRIS solutions can lead to data silos and compatibility issues, making it difficult to share and aggregate data across different systems and platforms. To mitigate these disadvantages, the following guidelines and standards, such as the CERIF data model and protocols like OAI-PMH or well-documented REST API (e.g. with aligned OpenAPI specifications and the OpenAIRE CRIS guidelines¹⁵) supports CRIS managers to expose their metadata to the OpenAIRE infrastructure as well as the EOSC and related services. By adhering to these established frameworks, institutions can improve data exchange and integration, facilitating broader collaboration and ensuring that research information is more accessible and usable within the wider research community.

5.2.2. Repositories

In our analysis, we examine all repositories mentioned in the list of other tools. Several of those repositories utilize widely adopted platforms like **InvenioRDM**, **DSpace**, or **Dataverse** (e.g. TU Graz or TU Wien repositories), but there are also numerous **custom-built solutions** tailored to specific institutional or domain-specific needs. Custom

¹⁵ <https://openaire-guidelines-for-cris-managers.readthedocs.io/>

repositories, while providing the benefit of bespoke features and alignment with unique workflows, often face challenges similar to custom CRIS systems, particularly in terms of interoperability. Adhering to the FAIR principles and other standards may help mitigate these issues, ensuring that custom repositories can effectively share and integrate data across different platforms and institutions. For example, TU Wien's institutional repository, TUWRD, leverages InvenioRDM while incorporating customized modules to meet specific needs, demonstrating how adherence to guidelines can enhance interoperability without sacrificing customization. As another example, TU Graz also has repository based on InvenioRDM, customized with corporate design and delivering additional functionality. Key aspects of custom repositories are:

- **Customization and Flexibility:** Custom-built repositories offer tailored solutions that meet specific institutional needs and workflows. This allows institutions to implement features and functionalities that align closely with their research practices and administrative processes.
- **Interoperability Challenges:** Custom solutions often face difficulties in data sharing and integration with other systems. Without adherence to common standards, these repositories can become data silos, limiting their effectiveness in broader scientific collaboration. The widely used repository platforms use **REST APIs** either documented within developer docs (e.g. InvenioRDM) and/or with OpenAPI specification (e.g. Dataverse).
- **Compliance with the FAIR Principles:** Following the FAIR principles helps ensure that data within custom repositories are more easily shared and integrated. This includes using persistent identifiers, machine-readable metadata, and standardized access protocols.
- **Adherence to Standards:** Utilizing established frameworks and protocols like **CERIF, OAI-PMH, and metadata schemas** (e.g., DataCite, Dublin Core, DCAT) can enhance the interoperability of custom repositories. This adherence allows for better data exchange and integration across different platforms and institutions. Some repositories even combine different data models (e.g. TU Graz, DataCite for research data, MARC21 for publications and LOM for open education resources).
- **Examples of Successful Implementation:** TUWRD and TU Graz Repository, both based on InvenioRDM, exemplifies how combining open-source solutions with custom modules can create a repository that meets specific institutional needs while adhering to standards that facilitate interoperability. This approach ensures high visibility, accessibility, and reuse of research data.
- **Certification of Repositories:** Obtaining certifications like **CoreTrustSeal** demonstrates a repository's commitment to maintaining high standards in data integrity, curation, and governance. Such certifications enhance trust and promote adherence to best practices and widely accepted standards.
- **Security Measures:** Implementing robust authentication and authorization mechanisms, data encryption, and adherence to data protection regulations like GDPR ensures the security and confidentiality of stored data. Regular security audits and secure data transfer protocols are essential practices.

- **Common Standards and Ontologies:** Utilizing metadata schemas such as DataCite and Dublin Core, along with ontologies like MeSH and AGROVOC, COAR controlled vocabularies for repositories, standardizes terminology and enhances data integration and discovery. Protocols like **OAI-PMH** facilitate metadata harvesting, ensuring wider dissemination and visibility of research data.

Security is a critical aspect of repository management, ensuring that data is protected against unauthorized access, breaches, and other vulnerabilities. Institutional repositories often implement robust authentication and authorization mechanisms, such as **single sign-on (SSO, through Shibboleth/SAML or OIDC) via institutional accounts or multi-factor authentication (MFA)**. These measures help ensure that only authorized users can access and manage data. Moreover, repositories need to adhere to stringent data protection regulations, such as GDPR, to safeguard the personal data of researchers and participants involved in the studies. Implementing secure data transfer protocols (e.g., HTTPS), encryption of data at rest and in transit, and regular security audits are also essential practices to maintain the integrity and confidentiality of the stored data. For API, usually **HTTP Bearer Authentication** is used with generated or issued token.

Common standards and ontologies play a vital role in enhancing the usability and interoperability of data (and possibly other research outputs) hosted in repositories. Metadata schemas like DataCite, Dublin Core, and Schema.org provide structured formats for describing research outputs, making them easier to find and access. Then domain-specific ontologies and controlled vocabularies, e.g. for life sciences, help standardize terminology, enabling more effective data integration and discovery. Additionally, repositories often implement protocols like **OAI-PMH** to facilitate metadata harvesting by aggregators and indexing services, ensuring wider dissemination and visibility of the research data.

5.2.3. Other

The category “Other” encompasses all remaining tools in the OSTrails project that does not clearly fit into the previous categories. The tools listed—CESSDA ELSST, CESSDA Vocabulary Service, CESSDA Metadata Aggregator, FAIRsharing, Lenticular Lens, OpenAIRE Broker, OpenOrgs, RCAAP, Recolecta, ROHub, Software Heritage, SOMEF, SSH Data Citation Service, Dabar, and OPUS CTA Provenance—represent a diverse range of platforms and services across various domains of research and data management. Despite their varied purposes, there are notable overlaps in the technologies they use, as well as in their approaches to interoperability and alignment.

Identified Common Technologies

- **Metadata Standards and Formats:**
 - **JSON:** Many tools such as SOMEF, SSH Data Citation Service, and Zenodo use JSON as a primary data exchange format. JSON's simplicity and compatibility with web technologies make it a common choice for representing metadata.

Moreover, JSON seems to be again a traditional choice in combination with REST API among these tools.

- **XML:** Tools like CESSDA Metadata Aggregator and Dabar use XML, including specific schemas like DDI, Dublin Core, and DataCite. XML's structured nature supports complex metadata descriptions and is widely used in academic and data management contexts. In contrast to JSON, XML is typically used when the tool supports OAI-PMH.
- **RDF:** SOMEF and OPUS CTA Provenance can generate RDF in Turtle and JSON-LD (RDF serializations) to represent metadata and provenance data, respectively. RDF's capability to model complex relationships and its adoption in semantic web technologies make it crucial for interoperable data representation. SOMEF also generates a JSON-LD compliant with CodeMeta, a standard representation for software metadata.
- **Persistent Identifiers:** Tools like CESSDA Metadata Aggregator and Dryad use persistent identifiers (DOI, URN, Handle) to ensure that datasets and metadata records are uniquely and reliably referenced over time. This practice supports long-term access and citation of research outputs. Other tools such as FAIRsharing or Software Heritage issue PIDs for their records to promote FAIR principles.
- **APIs and Endpoints:** Several tools provide REST APIs for data access and integration. For example, Dabar, OpenAIRE Broker, FAIRsharing, or CESSDA ELSST Thesaurus use REST APIs to allow automated interactions and data retrieval. The use of REST APIs facilitates integration with other systems and supports the automation of data workflows. For some of the tools other types of integrations like OAI-PMH (e.g. in case of CESSDA Metadata Aggregator) or GraphQL are also essential.
- **Authentication and Authorization:** Tools like Dabar and OPUS CTA Provenance use token-based authentication and role-based access control. This approach secures access to resources and ensures that users have appropriate permissions for their roles.

Interoperability

- **Standards Compliance:** Many tools align with international standards and recommendations, such as DataCite, Dublin Core, CodeMeta, Schema.org and OpenAIRE guidelines. This alignment ensures that metadata is represented consistently across platforms, facilitating data sharing and integration. Tools like FAIRsharing and Recolecta actively support and align with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, promoting data interoperability and enhancing the discoverability and usability of research data.
- **Integration with National and International Systems:** Dabar's integration with the Croatian national CRIS system CroRIS and plans for interoperability with Argos highlight the importance of connecting local systems with broader infrastructures. Similarly, OpenAIRE Broker aggregates metadata from various repositories, illustrating the role of central services in linking distributed data sources.

- **Use of Provenance Models:** OPUS CTA Provenance and some other tools adopt W3C PROV and IVOA Provenance Data Model standards to capture and represent the provenance of data and processes. This approach supports transparency and reproducibility in research by documenting the history and context of data.
- **Controlled Vocabularies and Taxonomies:** Tools like CESSDA ELSST and CESSDA Vocabulary Service contain vocabularies and taxonomies to ensure consistent and standardized representation of research topics and data descriptions. This practice enhances data quality and interoperability by providing a common framework for categorizing and describing research content.

Alignment

- **Data Exchange and Formats:** The use of common formats (JSON, XML) and protocols (OAI-PMH) across tools supports seamless data exchange and integration. Tools like CESSDA Metadata Aggregator and Dabar that use OAI-PMH for metadata harvesting exemplify how standard protocols facilitate interoperability among different data repositories.
- **Open and Accessible Data:** Many services, including Zenodo and Figshare, promote open access to research data and metadata. Also, the controlled vocabularies in CESSDA vocabulary service and the CESSDA ELSST thesaurus are openly available. This openness aligns with the principles of transparency and accessibility, enabling researchers and institutions to share and reuse data more effectively.
- **Cross-Platform Integration:** Tools like Software Heritage and FAIRsharing contribute to the broader ecosystem by ensuring that metadata and data can be accessed and integrated across different platforms and services. This cross-platform integration supports a holistic view of research outputs and their associated metadata.

The tools discussed, while diverse in their specific functions and domains, share several common technologies and approaches that enhance their interoperability and alignment. These tools collectively contribute to a more connected and efficient research data infrastructure by adhering to established standards, utilizing widely accepted data formats, and integrating with national and international systems. Their overlapping use of technologies such as JSON, XML, RDF, and persistent identifiers, along with their commitment to open access and standardized metadata representation, underscores the importance of interoperability in advancing research and data management practices.

5.3. Interoperability of Other Supporting Tools and Requirements

In examining the diverse range of tools such as CESSDA ELSST, CESSDA Vocabulary Service, FAIRsharing, Software Heritage, and many others, we observe a robust emphasis on interoperability and alignment using common technologies and adherence to international standards. These tools often utilize widely accepted data formats like JSON

and XML, with JSON commonly paired with **REST APIs for seamless integration** and XML used in conjunction with **OAI-PMH for metadata harvesting**. **Persistent identifiers** (DOI, URN, Handle) are frequently employed to ensure reliable and long-term access to research outputs. Tools also align with standards such as DataCite, Dublin Core, and OpenAIRE guidelines, supporting the consistent representation of metadata across platforms. This alignment facilitates data sharing, integration, and adherence to FAIR principles, which enhance the discoverability and usability of research data.

Interoperability is further supported by **using controlled vocabularies and taxonomies**, which standardize the representation of research topics and data descriptions. Tools like CESSDA Vocabulary Service exemplify this practice. Integration with national and international systems, such as CroRIS and OpenAIRE Broker, highlights the importance of connecting local systems to broader infrastructures for enhanced data aggregation and visibility. Additionally, the adoption of provenance models by tools like OPUS CTA Provenance ensures transparency and reproducibility in research data by documenting the history and context of data processes. Overall, the use of these common technologies and standards significantly contributes to a more interconnected and efficient research data management ecosystem.

Our key insights for decision making in design and implementation with respect to the other supporting tools can be summarized as follows:

- **Standardize Data Formats and Protocols:** Employ common data formats like JSON and XML and use established protocols such as REST APIs (with use of OpenAPI specification) and OAI-PMH to facilitate interoperability and integration across different systems.
- **Adopt Persistent Identifiers:** Implement persistent identifiers (DOI, URN, Handle) to ensure reliable and long-term access to research data and metadata, enhancing citation and data management practices.
- **Align with International Standards:** Follow metadata standards and guidelines like DataCite, Dublin Core, and OpenAIRE Guidelines to ensure consistent representation and sharing of research metadata.
- **Utilize Controlled Vocabularies:** Incorporate controlled vocabularies and taxonomies to standardize research topics and data descriptions, improving data quality and integration.
- **Integrate with Broader Systems:** Ensure compatibility with national and international systems (e.g., CRIS systems, metadata aggregators) to enhance data aggregation, visibility, and interoperability.
- **Implement Provenance Models:** Adopt provenance standards (e.g., W3C PROV) to document the history and context of data processes, supporting transparency and reproducibility.
- **Ensure Open Access and Cross-Platform Integration:** Promote open access to data (according to the principle 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary') and metadata, and ensure that metadata can be integrated and accessed across various platforms to support a holistic view of research outputs.

6. Common Interoperability Insights

Interoperability is a cornerstone of effective Open Science, enabling seamless data sharing, integration, and utilization across various systems and stakeholders. Based on the analysis of numerous tools, several key insights emerge that guide the design and implementation of interoperable systems.

6.1. General Insights

Across the spectrum of the tools, several key practices enhance interoperability and integration. Standardized data formats such as **JSON and XML**, often used with **REST APIs or OAI-PMH**, ensure consistent data representation and facilitate smooth data exchange between systems. **Persistent identifiers** like DOI, URN, and Handle are universally employed to provide reliable, long-term access to datasets, supporting accurate citation and ongoing data management.

Alignment with metadata **standards and vocabularies** (domain-agnostic and eventually domain-specific based on target audience) such as DataCite Metadata Schema, DCMI Metadata Terms, SKG-IF, and OpenAIRE Guidelines helps maintain metadata consistency and promotes effective data sharing. **Integration with national and international systems** enhances data visibility and aggregation, while controlled vocabularies and taxonomies standardize research topics and descriptions, improving data quality and discoverability. Additionally, the **adoption of provenance models** supports transparency and reproducibility by documenting data lineage. Collectively, these practices foster a cohesive and efficient research data management ecosystem, enabling better data integration and accessibility across diverse platforms.

6.2. Topic-Based Insights

In this subsection, we briefly mention the key insights per topic related to the interoperability and relevant to our project.

6.2.1. Standardized Data Formats and Protocols

Utilizing standardized data formats such as JSON and XML is crucial for ensuring consistent data representation and facilitating integration. JSON, often used with REST APIs, offers a **lightweight and flexible approach for data exchange**. XML, on the other hand, supports complex metadata descriptions and is commonly paired with OAI-PMH for metadata harvesting. Adherence to established protocols like **REST APIs and OAI-PMH enhances automated data interactions** and metadata aggregation, promoting interoperability across systems. **JSON-LD or other RDF formats** provide semantics for the data in an interoperable way; however, seems to be more complex for some tools to implement. Based on the analysis, it is used relatively rarely; RDF technologies are used

mainly within SKGs as JSON was not enough for representing complex relationships (as can be seen for instance with OAI-PMH) or to represent FAIR tests or results.

6.2.2. Persistent Identifiers

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) such as DOI, URN, and Handle are vital for maintaining reliable and long-term access to research outputs. These **unique identifiers facilitate accurate citation and ensure the enduring retrievability** of datasets and metadata records, supporting effective data management and discovery.

6.2.3. Alignment with International Standards

Compliance with international metadata standards, vocabularies, and guidelines, including DataCite, Dublin Core, SKG-IF, and OpenAIRE Guidelines, ensures **consistent metadata representation and facilitates cross-platform integration**. Following these standards promotes interoperability and enhances the visibility and accessibility of research data within broader infrastructures.

Moreover, adopting provenance models, such as those defined by W3C PROV, supports transparency and reproducibility in research. Documenting the history and context of data processes ensures data lineage is traceable, contributing to the **integrity and reliability of research outputs**.

6.2.4. Controlled Vocabularies and Taxonomies

Incorporating controlled vocabularies and taxonomies standardizes the representation of research topics and data descriptions. This practice, exemplified by tools like the CEESDA Vocabulary Service and in a broader scope the SSH Vocabulary Commons, improves data quality and integration by providing a common framework for categorizing and describing research content. However, we do need agreed ways to map between different, semantically overlapping vocabularies. Such mappings should be made shareable in the OS-Trails commons and beyond. For instance, using SSSOM¹⁶ as a mapping format and the MSCR¹⁷ as a mapping registry.

6.2.5. Integration with Broader Systems

Effective integration with national and international systems, such as CRIS and metadata aggregators like OpenAIRE Broker, enhances data aggregation and visibility. Connecting

¹⁶ <https://academic.oup.com/database/article/doi/10.1093/database/baac035/6591806>

¹⁷ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

local systems to broader infrastructures supports comprehensive data sharing and improves overall research data management.

6.2.6. Open Access and Cross-Platform Integration

Promoting open access to metadata and data and ensuring compatibility across various platforms align with **principles of transparency and collaboration**. Cross-platform integration enables a holistic view of research outputs and supports effective data sharing and reuse.

6.3. Requirements for OSTrails IF

The OSTrails interoperability framework (IF) is designed to facilitate seamless integration and data exchange across diverse systems and platforms. To achieve this, our analysis brings several key (non-functional) requirements that ensure compatibility, usability, security, and governance.

Firstly, the framework must **support standard data formats and protocols** to ensure interoperability. This includes widely accepted formats such as JSON, XML, and JSON-LD, as well as semantically rich formats like RDF. By aligning with established ontologies and vocabularies, the framework enhances data compatibility and integration across various platforms and systems.

Documentation is a critical component of the framework's usability. **Comprehensive, versioned documentation** must be provided to guide API adopters through integration. This documentation should include clear explanations of principles, conventions, and examples to ensure users can effectively implement and utilize the framework.

Security is an essential aspect in managing access to personal or sensitive data and operations. The framework should implement robust authentication and authorization mechanisms, such as OAuth 2.0 or OpenID Connect, to protect data integrity and ensure secure interactions. Additionally, a compliance verification process should be established to ensure adherence to standards and protocols.

Governance and quality assurance are also crucial. A well-defined governance framework must oversee the consistency and quality of tests, metrics, and tools used within the framework. **Validation and schema compliance mechanisms should be integrated** to maintain high data quality and alignment with international standards.

Finally, the framework should **support integration with institutional systems** and facilitate extensions together with enabled future development. This includes enabling event notifications for timely updates and providing mechanisms for future extensions to accommodate emerging technologies and practices.

To summarize the requirements:

- R1. The OSTrails IF *must* use existing established data models and specifications such as RDA DMP Common Standard for maDMPs or SKG-IF (eventually contribute to them or extend them, based on specific needs).
- R2. The OSTrails IF *must* provide comprehensive, versioned documentation for adopters, including principles, conventions, and examples.
- R3. The OSTrails IF *should* support common data formats and standards such as JSON, XML, JSON-LD, and RDF to ensure interoperability and data integration.
- R4. The OSTrails IF *should* specify a common way for secure authentication and authorization mechanisms, such as OAuth 2.0 or OpenID Connect.
- R5. The OSTrails IF *must* align with persistent identifier systems (e.g., DOI, ORCID, ROR) for improved data traceability and reliability.
- R6. The OSTrails IF *should* establish a compliance verification process to ensure adherence for adopting tools.
- R7. The OSTrails IF *should* use existing widely-used ontologies and vocabularies (e.g., Schema.org, DCTerms, DataCite) to enhance data interoperability.
- R8. The OSTrails IF *should* design APIs following OpenAPI specifications and REST architectural styles, with JSON as a supported format for data exchange.
- R9. The OSTrails IF *should* provide mechanisms for validation and schema compliance to ensure high data quality and adherence to international standards.
- R10. The framework *could* propose the representation and exchange of data in semantically rich formats like RDF to enhance interoperability.
- R11. The framework *could* facilitate deeper integration with institutional systems (e.g., CRIS) by specifying compatible APIs and data models.
- R12. The framework *could* enable event notifications for external services to subscribe to changes or updates in records.
- R13. The framework *must* allow for future extensions and contributions to accommodate emerging technologies and practices.

In summary, the non-functional requirements for the OSTrails interoperability framework (IF) are crucial for ensuring smooth and secure integration across different systems. These requirements focus on supporting standard data formats, providing clear documentation, and implementing strong security measures. Emphasizing good governance and the ability to adapt to future changes, these requirements aim to enhance data compatibility and maintain high-quality standards, fostering effective and reliable data sharing across various platforms.

6.4. Summary

To achieve robust interoperability, it is essential to standardize data formats, adhere to international guidelines, and use persistent identifiers. Incorporating controlled vocabularies, integrating with broader systems, and adopting provenance models further enhance data sharing and management. By following these practices, researchers and institutions can build a connected and efficient tools ecosystem for Open Science, advancing the accessibility and impact of research data.

7. Results and Next Steps

The analysis of various tools within or relevant to the OSTrails project reveals a well-established framework for achieving interoperability through the use of standardized technologies and practices. These practices facilitate effective integration, data sharing, and alignment across diverse platforms.

7.1. Core Technologies and Standards

Here are the core technologies and standards identified as suitable and proven for alignment across the mentioned tools:

- **DMP Common Standard:** For the creation and management of Data Management Plans (DMPs), adopting the DMP Common Standard ensures consistency and interoperability across different DMP platforms.
- **Science Knowledge Graph (SKG) IF:** Implementing the SKG Interchange Format promotes a unified approach to data representation and integration within science knowledge graphs.
- **REST APIs with OpenAPI:** Utilizing REST APIs documented and specified with OpenAPI ensures consistent and accessible data exchange and integration across systems.
- **OAI-PMH for Metadata Harvesting:** The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) is crucial for effective metadata sharing, synchronisation, and aggregation between repositories and consumers/clients.
- **Persistent Identifiers:** Employing persistent identifiers such as DOI, URN, and Handle supports reliable referencing and long-term access to research outputs.
- **Controlled Vocabularies and Taxonomies:** Using standardized vocabularies and taxonomies ensures consistent classification and description of research data, enhancing discoverability and interoperability. Common vocabularies can be then used for various use cases, e.g., defining test results in terms of FAIR assessment, or supporting the DMP Common Standard and its extension.

7.2. Identified Gaps

While confronting the information about tools with OSTrails Pathways and Interoperability Framework (IF), we identified the following gaps that need to be filled in.

- **Notifications:** Current tools often lack comprehensive notification systems to alert users about updates, changes, or issues related to data or metadata. There are various options and standards to follow when designing an interoperable solution such as notifications according to the W3C recommendations (Web Notifications¹⁸ and Linked Data Notifications¹⁹).

¹⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/notifications/>

¹⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/ldn/>

- **Provenance Documentation:** While some tools use provenance models (e.g. through PROV-O), there is variability in the implementation of standards for documenting the history and context of data processes (in SKGs, DMPs as well as some FAIR assessment tools and other supporting tools).
- **Integration with Emerging Standards:** As new standards and technologies emerge, there is a need for ongoing alignment and updates to ensure compatibility and relevance. In other words, the tools as well as specifications for interoperability needs to adopt mechanism for evolution over time.
- **Semantic Data Representation:** While tools tend to adopt existing vocabularies and ontologies where suitable for semantic and interoperable representation (e.g. as JSON-LD in addition to custom JSON representation), more extensive use of RDF technologies is rather missing. Linking external resources, (FAIR) Signposting, or SPARQL endpoints are very rare among the analysed tools. Still, adopting at least JSON-LD RDF representation is a reasonable first step.

7.3. Next Steps

This analysis creates a solid foundation for future design and implementation decisions. Therefore, the next steps where this analysis will be used are as follows:

- **Design and Architecture:** Leverage the identified technologies and standards to design and develop tools that adhere to proven practices for interoperability. Ensure that new tools and updates integrate seamlessly with existing systems by using common standards, such as REST APIs, OAI-PMH, and persistent identifiers. The outlined non-functional requirements should guide the creation of a detailed design, ensuring compatibility, clear documentation, and robust security measures. The non-functional requirements should inform these specifications, ensuring they reflect the necessary standards for interoperability and alignment with the OSTrails IF description outlined in Milestone 4. This will help shape Deliverable D1.4, the "OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V1" as shown in [Figure 5](#).
- **Specification of OSTrails Commons:** Develop detailed specifications for the OSTrails Commons that incorporate the core technologies and address identified gaps and requirements. This includes defining common representations for notifications, FAIR assessment results, and provenance documentation. Therefore, this analysis will serve as one of the inputs for the Deliverable D2.5 "OSTrails Commons Specifications" and later in its resulting from D2.6.
- **Implementation and Testing:** Implement the outlined technologies and standards in tool development, followed by rigorous testing to ensure alignment with the OSTrails Interoperability Framework. Utilize the non-functional requirements to monitor and refine the implementation, addressing any issues and incorporating feedback. This process should focus on validating that the tools meet the required standards and adapt based on emerging best practices. Through the OSTrails IF and Commons, the requirements will be then reflected in the implemented tools and the subsequent deliverables D2.2, D2.3, and D2.4.

- Community Engagement:** Engage with the research community to gather input on the OSTrails Commons specifications and gain insights into additional needs or potential improvements. Collaboration within the Horizon Europe programme, including with other projects, is also essential for ensuring the results' impact and alignment. This collaborative approach will help ensure the tools meet user requirements and enhance overall effectiveness.

Figure 5. Relation to the OSTrails IF and other WP2 activities.

By following these steps and integrating the non-functional requirements into design, specification, and implementation processes, the research data management ecosystem can achieve greater integration and functionality, ultimately supporting more effective data sharing and utilization across diverse platforms.

8. Conclusions

This analysis provides a thorough examination of tool compliance with the OSTrails Interoperability Framework (IF), assessing a diverse range of tools involved in the project. By evaluating 55 tools, including Data Management Planning (DMP) platforms, Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), FAIR assessment tools, and other supporting systems such as CRIS and repositories, the report identifies current technological alignments and highlights significant gaps. Notable issues include the need for comprehensive notification systems, variability in provenance documentation, and ongoing alignment with emerging standards. These findings underline the necessity for further development to meet the OSTrails Pathways and IF requirements effectively.

The methodology encompassed a systematic evaluation process, starting with the creation of a Master Table and flashcard presentations for each tool. This approach ensured a clear understanding of each tool's compliance and interoperability. The consolidated results provide valuable feedback on the OSTrails IF specification and essential inputs for refining OSTrails Commons and guiding tool implementation. This analysis serves as a foundational reference for enhancing interoperability, addressing gaps, and advancing the framework's goals for effective data sharing and integration across various platforms.

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10. Annex

The following documents are additional resources supporting our analysis:

- A. Tools onboarding document
- B. Master table
- C. Tools flashcard presentations (template + 54 presentations merged)
- D. Per-tool analysis documents (template + 38 documents merged)